

Solution of time fractional order biological population equations using Aboodh transform method

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Abstract: In this article, we propose a numerical method to find the approximate solution of time fractional order biological population model equations. The type was solved by a recent approximate analytical method called the Aboodh Fractional Decomposition Method (FADM), the paper obtains numerical solutions in the form of converging series. Three examples are discussed to illustrate the validity and applicability of the proposed method.

Key words: Aboodh Transform, fractional partial differential equation, Caputo fractional derivative, series, time fractional order biological population model equation

1. Introduction

In recent years, fractional calculus has been applied in many different fields, such as physics, dynamic systems, control systems, and engineering and biological phenomena[5, 10]. Recently, many different techniques have been introduced and applied, including the Adomian's Decomposition Method (ADM), the homotopy perturbation method (HPM), the variational iteration method (VIM) [7], the spectral methods, the orthogonal polynomial method and the wavelet method. Other methods are used for solving two-dimensional partial differential equations. The Aboodh transform method is considered one of the most important transformations for solving some differential equations and it is an effective method for solving several types of EDP in various scientific and engineering fields. In addition, different methods are combined with Aboodh transform method such as homotopy perturbation transformation method which is a combination of homotopy perturbation[11, 12].

In this work, we depended on the fractional Aboodh decomposition method (FADM) . We wish to extend the applicability of this method to time-fractional nonlinear biological population diffusion equation as follows[9]:

$$D_t^\alpha f(x, y, t) = \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial y^2} + hf^a (1 - rf^b), t \geq 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad (1)$$

with $f(x, y, 0) = k_0(x, y)$, where a, b, h, r are real numbers. The FADM is a graceful coupling of two powerful techniques, namely ADM and Aboodh transform algorithms who give solution as more refined convergent series .To demonstrate the effectiveness of this algorithm, several numerical examples of fractional biological population model equations are presented.

2. Preliminary

Definition 2.1. Over the set of functions:

$$F = \{f(x) : |f(x)| < Me^{-vt}, \text{ if } x \in [0; \infty[, M, k_1, k_2 > 0; k_1 \leq v \leq k_2\}. \quad (2)$$

The constant M is a finite number, k_1, k_2 may be finite or infinite with variable v define as $k_1 \leq v \leq k_2$. The Aboodh transform is defined by [3, 6]:

$$T(v) = A[f(x)] = \frac{1}{v} \int_0^\infty e^{-vx} f(x) dx, \quad x \geq 0, k_1 \leq v \leq k_2. \quad (3)$$

Standard Aboodh transform for some special functions are given below in Table (2).

Table 1: Aboodh transform of some functions.

$f(x)$	$T(v) = A[f(x)]$
1	$\frac{1}{v^2}$
x	$\frac{1}{v^3}$
x^β	$\frac{\Gamma(\beta + 1)}{v^{\beta+2}}$
$\exp(ax)$	$\frac{1}{v^2 - av}$
$\sin(ax)$	$\frac{1}{v(v^2 + a^2)}$
$\cos(ax)$	$\frac{1}{v^2 + a^2}$
$\sinh(ax)$	$\frac{1}{v(v^2 - a^2)}$
$x \cosh(ax)$	$\frac{1}{v^2 - a^2}$

Definition 2.2. A real function $f(x), x > 0$, is said to be in the space in $C_\mu, \mu \in \mathbb{R}$ if there exists a real number $p(> \mu)$, such that $f(x) = x^p f_1(x)$ where $f_1(x) \in C[0, \infty)$, and it is said to be in the space C_μ^m if and only if $f^{(m)} \in C_\mu, m \in \mathbb{N}$.

Definition 2.3. The caputo fractional derivative (CFD) operator D_x^α of order α is

$$D_x^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \int_0^x \frac{f^{(n)}(t)}{(x - t)^{1+\alpha-n}} dt, \quad x > 0, \quad (4)$$

for $n - 1 < \alpha \leq n, n \in \mathbb{N}, f \in C_{-1}^n$.

Definition 2.4. The Aboodh transform of the Caputo fractional derivative is defined as :

$$A[D_x^\alpha f(x)] = v^\alpha T(v) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f^{(k)}(0)}{v^{2-\alpha+k}}. \quad (5)$$

It is trivial that:

$$A [D_t^{n\alpha} f(x; y; t)] = v^{n\alpha} A [f(x; y; t)] - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f^{(k)}(x; y; 0)}{v^{2-n\alpha+k}}, \quad (6)$$

where $n - 1 < n\alpha \leq n$.

3. Procedure: Aboodh Decomposition Method(ADM) for solving FNLPPDEs

The fractional nonlinear partial differential equation (FNLPPDEs) is presented as:

$$D_t^\alpha f(x; y; t) + P [f(x; y; t)] + Q [f(x; y; t)] = g(x; y; t), \quad (7)$$

where $n - 1 < \alpha \leq n$, and $g(x; y; t)$ is the source term, Q is a nonlinear differential operator, P is the linear differential term and $D_t^\alpha f(x; y; t)$ is the Caputo fractional derivative of the function $f(x; y; t)$. With initial condition

$$\left. \frac{\partial^{(r)} f(x, y, t)}{\partial t^r} \right|_{t=0} = f_r(x, y), \quad r = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n - 1. \quad (8)$$

Now applying the AT(Aboodh Transform) into (7), we have:

$$A [D_t^\alpha f(x; y; t)] + A [P [f(x; y; t)]] + A [Q [f(x; y; t)]] = A [g(x; y; t)] \quad (9)$$

Substituting (6) into (9), we get:

$$v^\alpha A [f(x; y; t)] - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f^{(k)}(x; y; 0)}{v^{2-\alpha+k}} + A [P [f(x; y; t)]] + A [Q [f(x; y; t)]] = A [g(x; y; t)] \quad (10)$$

$$A [f(x; y; t)] = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f_k(x, y)}{v^{2+k}} - v^{-\alpha} A [P [f(x; y; t)]] - v^{-\alpha} A [Q [f(x; y; t)]] + v^{-\alpha} A [g(x; y; t)]. \quad (11)$$

Applying the inverse Aboodh transform A^{-1} to (11), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} f(x; y; t) = & A^{-1} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f_k(x, y)}{v^{2+k}} \right] - A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [P [f(x; y; t)]]] \\ & - A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [Q [f(x; y; t)]]] + A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [g(x; y; t)]]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

So, according to Aboodh decomposition method (ADM), we can obtain the solution result $f(x; y; t)$ as

$$f(x; y; t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} f_m(x; y; t). \quad (13)$$

The nonlinear operator is decomposed as:

$$Q [f(x; y; t)] = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} B_m (f_0; f_1, \dots, f_m), \quad (14)$$

where

$$B_m(f_0; f_1; \dots, f_m) = \frac{1}{m!} \frac{\partial^m}{\partial \lambda^m} Q \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \lambda^i f_i \right) \right].$$

Then, the Adomian series reads

$$\begin{cases} B_0 = f_0^2 \\ B_1 = 2f_0f_1 \\ B_2 = 2f_0f_2 + f_1^2 \\ \vdots \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Now, by substituting (13) and (14) into (12), we obtain :

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} f_m(x; y; t) &= A^{-1} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f_k(x, y)}{v^{2+k}} \right] - A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[P \left[\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} f_m(x; y; t) \right] \right] \right] \\ &\quad - A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} B_m \right] \right] + A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A [g(x; y; t)] \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Comparing both side of (16), we get

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(x; y; t) &= A^{-1} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f_k(x, y)}{v^{2+k}} \right] + A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A [g(x; y; t)] \right] \\ f_1(x; y; t) &= -A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A [P(f_0(x; y; t)) + B_0] \right] \\ f_2(x; y; t) &= -A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A [P(f_1(x; y; t)) + B_1] \right] \\ &\quad \vdots \\ f_m(x; y; t) &= -A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A [P(f_{m-1}(x; y; t)) + B_{m-1}] \right], \quad m \geq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Therefore, the approximate solution is given as the form of (13).

4. Applications

We shall test three examples using the ADM for solving two dimensional fractional partial differential equations.

Example 4.1. We consider the linear time fractional order biological population model equation of the form:

$$D_t^\alpha f(x, y, t) = \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial y^2} + hf, \quad , t \geq 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad (18)$$

subject to initial condition

$$f(x, y, 0) = \sqrt{xy} \quad (19)$$

and h is a parameter.

Applying the AT into (18), and with (17), get the successive approximations

$$f_0(x, y, t) = f(x, y, 0) = \sqrt{xy}$$

we can find the recurrence relation of the form:

$$f_m(x, y, t) = A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 f_{m-1}^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f_{m-1}^2}{\partial y^2} + h f_{m-1} \right] \right]. \quad (20)$$

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(x, y, t) &= \sqrt{xy} \\ f_1(x, y, t) &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 f_0^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f_0^2}{\partial y^2} + h f_0 \right] \right] = A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [h f_0]] = h f_0 A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [1]] \\ &\Rightarrow f_1(x, y, t) = h f_0 A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+\alpha}} \right] = h f_0 \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} = h \sqrt{xy} \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)}. \\ f_2(x, y, t) &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 f_1^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f_1^2}{\partial y^2} + h f_1 \right] \right] \\ &= A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [h f_1]] = h^2 f_0 A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} \right] \right] \\ &= \frac{h^2 f_0}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [t^\alpha]] = \frac{h^2 f_0}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} \frac{\Gamma(1+\alpha)}{v^{2+\alpha}} \right] \\ &= h^2 f_0 A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+2\alpha}} \right] = h^2 f_0 \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} \\ &\Rightarrow f_2(x, y, t) = h^2 f_0 A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+2\alpha}} \right] = h^2 f_0 \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} = h^2 \sqrt{xy} \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the solution of (18) is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x; y; t) &= \sqrt{xy} + h \sqrt{xy} \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} + h^2 \sqrt{xy} \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} + \dots \\ &\dots + h^m \sqrt{xy} \frac{t^{m\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+m\alpha)} + \dots = (\sqrt{xy}) E_\alpha(ht^\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $E_\alpha(z)$ denotes the Mittag-Leffler function[1]. If we put $\alpha = 1$ in (21), we can conclude the exact solution

$$\begin{aligned} f(x; y; t) &= \sqrt{xy} + h \sqrt{xy} \frac{t}{\Gamma(2)} + h^2 \sqrt{xy} \frac{t^2}{\Gamma(3)} + \dots + h^m \sqrt{xy} \frac{t^m}{\Gamma(1+m)} + \dots \\ &= \sqrt{xy} \left(1 + ht + \frac{h^2 t^2}{2!} + \frac{h^3 t^3}{3!} + \dots + \frac{h^m t^m}{m!} + \dots \right) = (\sqrt{xy}) e^{ht}. \end{aligned}$$

(a) $f(x, y, 0) = \sqrt{xy}$

Figure 1: Plot3D of the exact solution given by (21) for $h = 1, t = 0$ and $(x, t) \in [0, 16] \times [0, 16]$.

(a) $f(x, 1, t) = \sqrt{x}e^t$

(b) $f(x, 1, t) = \sqrt{x}E_{0.8}(t^{0.8})$

Figure 2: Plot3D of the exact solution given by (21) for $h = 1, y = 1$ and $(x, t) \in [0, 5] \times [0, 5]$.

Example 4.2. We consider the linear time fractional order biological population model equation of the form:

$$D_t^\alpha f(x, y, t) = \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial y^2} + f, \quad t \geq 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad (22)$$

with initial condition

$$f(x, y, 0) = \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y}. \quad (23)$$

We apply the AT into (22), and with (17), we obtain the successive approximations

$$f_0(x, y, t) = f(x, y, 0) = \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y}$$

$$f_m(x, y, t) = A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 f_{m-1}^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f_{m-1}^2}{\partial y^2} + f_{m-1} \right] \right]. \quad (24)$$

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(x, y, t) &= \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \\ f_1(x, y, t) &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 f_0^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f_0^2}{\partial y^2} + f_0 \right] \right] = A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [f_0]] = hf A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [1]] \\ &\Rightarrow f_1(x, y, t) = f_0 A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+\alpha}} \right] = f_0 \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} = \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)}. \\ f_2(x, y, t) &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 f_1^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f_1^2}{\partial y^2} + f_1 \right] \right] = A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [f_1]] = f_0 A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} \right] \right] \\ &= \frac{f_0}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [t^\alpha]] = \frac{f_0}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} \frac{\Gamma(1+\alpha)}{v^{2+\alpha}} \right] = f_0 A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+2\alpha}} \right] = f_0 \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} \\ &\Rightarrow f_2(x, y, t) = f_0 A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+2\alpha}} \right] = f_0 \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} = \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the solution of (22) is :

$$\begin{aligned} f(x; y; t) &= \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} + \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} + \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} + \dots \\ &\dots + \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t^{m\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+m\alpha)} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

If we put $\alpha = 1$ in (25), we can conclude the exact solution

$$\begin{aligned} f(x; y; t) &= \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} + \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t}{\Gamma(2)} + \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t^2}{\Gamma(3)} + \dots \\ &\dots + \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \frac{t^m}{\Gamma(1+m)} + \dots \\ &= \sqrt{\sin x \sinh y} \left(1 + t + \frac{t^2}{2!} + \frac{t^3}{3!} + \dots + \frac{t^m}{m!} + \dots \right) = (\sqrt{\sin x \sinh y}) e^t. \end{aligned}$$

(a) $f(x, y, 0) = \sqrt{\sin(x) \sinh(y)}$

Figure 3: Plot3D of the exact solution given by (25) for $t = 0$ and $(x, t) \in [0, 42] \times [0, 6]$.

(a) $f(x, 1, t) = \sqrt{\sin(x) \sinh(1)}e^t$

(b) $f(x, 1, t) = \sqrt{\sin(x) \sinh(1)}E_{0.7}(t^{0.7})$

Figure 4: Plot3D of the exact solution given by (25) for $y = 1$ and $(x, t) \in [0, 42] \times [0, 6]$.

Example 4.3. We consider the following fractional biological population equation:

$$D_t^\alpha f(x, y, t) = \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f^2}{\partial y^2} + f \left(1 - \frac{r}{4}f\right), \quad t \geq 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad (26)$$

with initial condition

$$f(x, y, 0) = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)}. \quad (27)$$

Applying the AT into (26), and with (17), we obtain the successive approximations

$$f_0(x, y, t) = f(x, y, 0) = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)}$$

$$f_m(x, y, t) = A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 B_{m-1}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 B_{m-1}}{\partial y^2} + f_{m-1} - \frac{r}{4} B_{m-1} \right] \right]. \quad (28)$$

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(x, y, t) &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \\ f_1(x, y, t) &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 B_0}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 B_0}{\partial y^2} + f_0 - \frac{r}{4} B_0 \right] \right] \\ &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 f_0^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f_0^2}{\partial y^2} + f_0 - \frac{r}{4} f_0^2 \right] \right] \\ &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{r e^{\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)}}{4} + e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} - \frac{r}{4} e^{\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \right] \right] \\ &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [1]] = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [1]] \\ &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+\alpha}} \right] = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} \\ f_2(x, y, t) &= A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 B_1}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 B_1}{\partial y^2} + f_1 - \frac{r}{4} B_1 \right] \right] \\ &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} A \left[\frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} \right] \right] \\ &= \frac{e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)}}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} A^{-1} [v^{-\alpha} A [t^\alpha]] = \frac{e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)}}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} A^{-1} \left[v^{-\alpha} \frac{\Gamma(1+\alpha)}{v^{2+\alpha}} \right] \\ &= f_0 A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+2\alpha}} \right] = \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} A^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{v^{2+2\alpha}} \right] \\ &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)}. \end{aligned}$$

So, the solution of (26) is :

$$\begin{aligned} f(x; y; t) &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} + e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} + e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha)} + \dots \\ &\dots + e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t^{m\alpha}}{\Gamma(1+m\alpha)} + \dots = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} E_\alpha(t^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

If we put $\alpha = 1$ in (29), we can conclude the exact solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(x; y; t) &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} + e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t}{\Gamma(2)} + e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t^2}{\Gamma(3)} + \dots \\
 &\dots + e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \frac{t^m}{\Gamma(1+m)} + \dots \\
 &= e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)} \left(1 + t + \frac{t^2}{2!} + \frac{t^3}{3!} + \dots + \frac{t^m}{m!} + \dots \right) = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\frac{r}{8}}(x+y)+t}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5: Plot3D of the exact solution given by (29) for $r = 8, y = 0$ and $(x, t) \in [-2, 2] \times [0, 1]$.

Conclusion

In this work, the ADM was applied to derive approximate analytical solutions of time fractional order biological population equations subject to some initial conditions. The obtained results with the proposed method demonstrate the validity and applicability of them for solving the FNLPPDEs.

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